

Case Studies “Authorship and Data Usage Conflicts”

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Please find below five case studies on "Authorship and Data Usage Conflicts in Ombuds Proceedings" (the German version is available in a separate document). The case studies were developed by Katrin Frisch and Nele Reeg (from the project "Discussion Hubs to Foster Research Integrity", German Research Ombudsman) for the workshop "Authorship and Data Usage Conflicts in Ombuds Proceedings" (conducted at the Ombuds Symposium 2023) based on a survey of ombudspersons. You are welcome to use the sample cases as templates to develop your own case scenarios. In case you use them in unchanged form for an event, please include a reference to our “discussion hub” project.

These scenarios are not designed to include all information required to „solve“ a given case. Rather they are meant to stimulate a discussion on how to handle a case, when to inquire for more information or where further evidence might be required.

In a second step, we will develop options for action on the case studies and indications where further research is needed to better assess the situation. These will also be made available on our website.

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Sample Case 1

Fear of consequences if ombuds proceeding is initiated

Scenario:

Doctoral student A collects data as part of his social science doctoral thesis using questionnaires and qualitative interviews. His supervisor, Prof B, came up with the initial idea and overall research question. The questions for the interviews and questionnaires were designed independently by doctoral student A. For support on their elaboration, but also for the analysis of the responses, he primarily exchanges ideas with other doctoral students who use similar methods. He occasionally reports on his progress to his supervisor Prof B, but generally does not find these meetings helpful, as little constructive criticism is given. Doctoral student A finally writes a manuscript and sends the draft to his supervisor Prof B. B suggests minor linguistic changes. Doctoral student A notes that supervisor B has also added himself as an author. Doctoral student A turns to an ombudsperson for advice on this case. During the counselling, he makes it clear that he is afraid of confronting supervisor B by openly questioning his authorship because he fears it would have a negative impact on the evaluation of his doctoral thesis and future letters of recommendation. Therefore, he only seeks consultation, but refuses to initiate proceedings.

Questions:

What other information/evidence should be obtained in order to better assess the situation? What advice can the ombudsperson give to the doctoral candidate? How can the doctoral candidate protect himself from consequences?

What are the ombudsperson's options in this situation (doctoral candidate wants to be advised but refuses to contact the other side)?

What would be the consequences for dealing with the enquiry if the doctoral candidate were to report that other current doctoral candidates supervised by Prof B have made similar experiences with regard to authorship?

What contributions would a supervisor have to have made during the discussions or in the course of supervision in order to qualify for co-authorship on publications resulting from a doctoral thesis? What are the discipline-specific differences?

Sample Case 2

Combination of GSP-conflict and personal conflicts

Scenario:

Researchers have collected data together and are now about to draft a joint publication. For a while now, the project has been plagued by a variety of communication problems between the designated authors, which can be traced back to the project leader P in particular and which are straining the workplace atmosphere. The personal discord between project leader P and a doctoral student W, whose dissertation is also supervised by P, escalates when he begins to question her abilities with discriminatory remarks. Finally, project leader P decides to exclude doctoral student W from further involvement in the analysis and assigns her tasks to another researcher. W who was originally planned as first author is now allocated a middle position. When the doctoral student W describes the conflict to an ombudsperson, she also states that she is afraid of being dropped as an author altogether, while being dependent on the publication – especially on the first authorship position – due to her cumulative doctorate.

Questions:

What can the ombudsperson suggest to the doctoral candidate? Is the project leader allowed to change responsibilities for tasks without prior consultation? Under what circumstances and in consultation with whom is this justified? Under what circumstances is a continued collaboration still reasonable or at which point should it be terminated?

What changes if not P is the supervisor, but a third person?

How should allegations of discrimination be dealt with? Should another body be involved or contacted for advice? If so, which one? Does discrimination (e.g. racism or sexism) require a special approach to case handling?

What documents could be helpful for the prevention of this type of conflict?

Sample Case 3

Data transfer in the context of scholarship funding

Scenario:

Supervisor C and doctoral student D (funded by a scholarship) work together on a project for which D collects and evaluates data. The supervisor C raises the suspicion that the evaluation of the data collected by the doctoral student D has not been conducted according to state-of-the-art methods. A highly emotional conflict develops in which the accusation of poor supervision and lack of appreciation is played off against the accusation of lack of knowledge. As a consequence, the doctoral student no longer wants to work with the supervisor or produce a joint publication. Instead, D wants to find a new supervisor and take the topic (and the data already generated) to another chair. Supervisor C is open to the departure of doctoral candidate D, but lays claim to the data as the initiator of the project idea, and objects to the data transfer. The doctoral student turns to an ombudsperson for help.

Questions:

How could the conflict over the data transfer be resolved? Which documents would have been helpful as a preventive measure?

Do discipline specific differences matter in the assessment of the conflict, e.g. in case of experimental data from the natural sciences versus interview data from the social sciences?

What if supervisor C's doubts about his doctoral student's methods can be substantiated (i.e. work is not done *lege artis*)? Under what circumstances is it possible for supervisor C to terminate the supervision? If the supervision were to be terminated, where would the research topic or the related data remain?

What if the data processing of D shows questionable research practices (e.g. cherry picking or HARKing) or D raises suspicions about QRPs?

Sample Case 4

Authorship dispute after departure

Scenario:

A team of researchers collects data together, jointly writes a manuscript and submits it to a journal. One of the researchers involved, scientist X, leaves the institution. After her departure, the journal editors return the manuscript raising questions especially about the experiments contributed by scientist X. In order to be able to address these, it is necessary to repeat the experiments in a partially modified form. The team carries out the necessary experiments yet without consulting scientist X. Researcher Z takes over many tasks in the process. As a result, the working group places Z in the first authorship position, while X is demoted from the first to a middle position. Scientist X finds the published article and only then learns about the revision and her new authorship position. She turns to an ombudsperson for advice.

Questions:

Were the researchers allowed to disregard her in the revision of the paper? What are her options in this situation?

How should the revision of the manuscript have been handled in accordance with GSP? Would it make a difference if researcher X had been on sick leave for a longer period of time or on parental leave?

How would the situation change if researcher X learns by chance that the manuscript has been largely reworked, but is still awaiting submission and she contacts the ombudsman's office at this point?

Sample Case 5

Questioning (the intent) of the ombudsperson in the context of an authorship dispute

Scenario

Researcher E approaches the ombudsperson with a complex authorship dispute. He has been involved in an interdisciplinary project, in which he has in particular contributed to data collection and analysis. However, there is disagreement among the team members about how significant and independent his contribution is. Based on the few supporting documents submitted by him, it is difficult for the ombudsperson to understand the scope of his contribution; the (scanty) supporting documents submitted by the opposing party do not help to clarify the situation either, but rather shed light on the differing views of the two parties. The communication between the ombudsperson and the inquiring scientist E starts to get strained. E becomes increasingly emotional and begins to question the ombudsperson's abilities and intentions.

Questions:

How can the ombudsperson best deal with this situation in which, in addition to the conflict between the researchers, his/her abilities and intentions are also questioned?

What (preventive) documents would be helpful here?

Under what circumstances should E's involvement in data collection be compensated with co-authorship? How can discipline specific differences be dealt with?